

Parameter Selections of Fuzzy C-Means Based on Robust Analysis

Kuo-Lung Wu

Abstract—The weighting exponent m is called the fuzzifier that can have influence on the clustering performance of fuzzy c-means (FCM) and $m \in [1.5, 2.5]$ is suggested by Pal and Bezdek [13]. In this paper, we will discuss the robust properties of FCM and show that the parameter m will have influence on the robustness of FCM. According to our analysis, we find that a large m value will make FCM more robust to noise and outliers. However, if m is larger than the theoretical upper bound proposed by Yu et al. [14], the sample mean will become the unique optimizer. Here, we suggest to implement the FCM algorithm with $m \in [1.5, 4]$ under the restriction when m is smaller than the theoretical upper bound.

Keywords—Fuzzy c-means, robust, fuzzifier.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN fuzzy clustering, the fuzzy c-means (FCM) algorithm is the best-known method [1,2]. Although FCM is a good clustering algorithm, there are some drawbacks when we apply FCM. Therefore, many extensions to the FCM algorithm had been proposed in the literatures. Overall, these extended types of FCM can be divided into two categories. One is to extend the dissimilarity (or distance) measure between the data point and the cluster center in the FCM objective function by replacing the Euclidean distance with the other types of metric measures (see Refs. [3,4,5,6,7]). Another one is to extend the FCM objective function by adding a penalized term (see Refs. [8,9,10,11]).

Another important influence factor to the effectiveness of FCM is the weighting exponent m which had been well investigated by Pal and Bezdek [13] and Yu et al. [14]. Pal and Bezdek [13] suggested to take $m \in [1.5, 2.5]$ and Yu et al. [14] proposed a theoretical upper bound for m that can prevent the sample mean being the unique optimizer of FCM objective function. In this paper, we will analysis the robustness of FCM based on the statistical point of view and show that FCM can be robust to noise and outliers in a large m case. In Section II, we brief review the FCM clustering method. We also discuss the parameter selections of FCM in Section III. In Section IV, we will discuss the robust properties of FCM and show that the parameter m will have influence on the robustness of FCM. We find that a large m value will make FCM more robust to noise and outliers. Conclusions are illustrated in Section V.

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II. FUZZY C-MEANS CLUSTERING ALGORITHM

Let $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ be a data set in an s -dimensional space R^s . Let c be a positive integer greater than one. A partition of X into c parts can be presented by mutually disjoint set X_1, \dots, X_c such that $X_1 \cup \dots \cup X_c = X$, or equivalently by the indicator functions μ_1, \dots, μ_c such that $\mu_{ij} = \mu_i(x_j) = 1$ if $x_j \in X_i$ and $\mu_{ij} = 0$ if $x_j \notin X_i$ for $i = 1, \dots, c$ and $j = 1, \dots, n$. The set of indicator functions μ_1, \dots, μ_c is called a hard c -partition of clustering X into c clusters. Now consider an extension to allow $\mu_{ij} = \mu_i(x_j) \in [0, 1]$ to be membership functions of fuzzy sets μ_i on X such that $\sum_{i=1}^c \mu_{ij} = 1$ for all x_j . In this section, we will give a brief review of the best-known fuzzy clustering method fuzzy c-means (FCM) and then discuss the parameter selections in FCM. We will also discuss the influence of fuzzifier m on the robustness of FCM.

In unsupervised learning clustering literatures, the fuzzy c-means (FCM) algorithm is the best-known fuzzy clustering method. The FCM is an iterative algorithm using the necessary conditions for a minimizer of the objective function J_{FCM} with

$$J_{FCM}(\mu, a) = \sum_{i=1}^c \sum_{j=1}^n \mu_{ij}^m \|x_j - a_i\|^2 \quad (1)$$

where the weighting exponent $m > 1$ is a fuzziness index, $\mu = \{\mu_1, \dots, \mu_c\}$ with $\mu_{ij} = \mu_i(x_j)$ is a fuzzy c -partition and $a = \{a_1, \dots, a_c\}$ is the set of c cluster centers. The necessary conditions for a minimizer (μ, a) of J_{FCM} are the following update equations:

$$\mu_{ij} = \frac{\|x_j - a_i\|^{-2/(m-1)}}{\sum_{k=1}^c \|x_j - a_k\|^{-2/(m-1)}} \quad (2)$$

and

$$a_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \mu_{ij}^m x_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n \mu_{ij}^m} \quad (3)$$

Note that, $d(x_j, a_i) = \|x_j - a_i\|^2$ is most used. However, other types of metric may be used to improve the usage and effectiveness of FCM (see Refs. [3,4,5,6,7]). On the other hand, another important factor influencing the effectiveness of FCM is the fuzziness index m , which has previously been thoroughly

Fig. 1. The membership functions and ϕ functions of FCM. (a), (b), (c) and (d) are membership functions with different fuzzifier $m=1.5, 2, 4$ and 6 , respectively. (e), (f), (g) and (h) are ϕ functions with different fuzzifier $m=1.5, 2, 4$ and 6 , respectively.

TABLE I
 THE UPPER LIMIT OF M FOR THE DATA SETS

Data set	Number of Samples	Number of Features	Number of Clusters	$\lambda_{\max}(C_X)$	Upper limit of m
Isolet 1+2+3+4	6238	617	26	0.1889	1.6072
Isolet 5	1559	617	26	0.1926	1.6265
Sonar	208	60	2	0.1949	1.6388
Vowel	990	10	11	0.2189	1.7787
PimaIndiansDiabetes	768	8	2	0.2558	2.0475
Waveform	5000	21	3	0.3272	2.8935
Glass	214	9	6	0.3424	3.1726
Iris	150	4	3	0.6652	$+\infty$

investigated in Pal and Bezdek [13] and Yu et al. [14].

III. PARAMETER SELECTIONS IN FCM

The weighting exponent m is called the fuzzifier that can have influence on the clustering performance of FCM. The influence of the weighting exponent m on the FCM membership function is shown in Fig. 1. This figure is produced by assuming that there are only two clusters with centers 0 and 2. The curves with different m values are the membership functions belonging to the cluster with center 0. When $m = 1$, the FCM will reduce to the traditional hard c -means. When m tends to infinity, $\mu_{ij} = 1/c$ for all i, j and the sample mean will be a unique optimizer of FCM objective function. In fact, this situation may occur for any specified m values and Yu et al. [14] proposed a theoretical upper bound for m that can prevent the sample mean from being the unique optimizer of FCM objective function. The rule is that $\forall i, a_i = \bar{x}$ is stable for FCM if $\lambda_{\max}(C_X) < 0.5$ and $m \geq (1 - 2\lambda_{\max}(C_X))^{-1}$, where $C_X = \sum_{j=1}^n (x_j - \bar{x})(x_j - \bar{x})^T / n \|x_j - \bar{x}\|^2$ and $\lambda_{\max}(C_X)$ is the maximum eigenvalue of the matrix C_X . Therefore, for FCM, we should set $m < (1 - 2\lambda_{\max}(C_X))^{-1}$ if $\lambda_{\max}(C_X) < 0.5$. If $\lambda_{\max}(C_X) \geq 0.5$, we can take m to be any

positive values and $m \in [1.5, 2.5]$ is suggested by Pal and Bezdek [13].

Table I (refer to Yu et al. [14]) shows the upper limit of m for some data sets obtained from the UCI Repository of Machine Learning Databases. For the data sets with $\lambda_{\max}(C_X) < 0.5$, sample mean will be the unique optimizer of FCM when the fuzzifier $m \geq (1 - 2\lambda_{\max}(C_X))^{-1}$ (the upper limit). The traditional specified m for FCM is 2 and we find that there are four data sets with the upper limit of m smaller than 2. In IRIS data set [15,16], since the maximum eigenvalue of the matrix C_X is larger than 0.5, the upper limit of m for the Iris data set is positive infinity. Yang and Wu [11] also confirmed a part of these results. We now give a simple example to demonstrate above properties.

We implement the Normal-4 data set to test the inferences of m on the performances of FCM. Pal and Bezdek [13] proposed the Normal-4 data set, which is a 4-dimensional data set with the sample size $n=800$ and each of four clusters contains 200 points. The population mean vectors are $c_1 = (3, 0, 0, 0)$, $c_2 = (0, 3, 0, 0)$, $c_3 = (0, 0, 3, 0)$ and $c_4 = (0, 0, 0, 3)$. The covariance matrix for each population is the identity matrix I_4 . We randomly generate 100 Normal-4 data sets and implement the FCM algorithm for each one of the data set with the parameters $m=1.5, 2, 2.5, 3$ and 3.5 . We then calculate the average MSE and average number of iterations for these 100

TABLE II
 MEAN SQUARE ERROR (MSE) AND NUMBER OF ITERATIONS OF 100
 RANDOMLY GENERATED NORMAL-4 DATA SETS

	MSE			Number of iterations		
	best case	average	worst case	best case	average	worst case
$m=1.5$	0.05791	0.14554	0.33201	10	14.93	23
$m=2$	0.16153	0.45912	0.91060	13	20.20	35
$m=2.5$	3.87754	5.95604	6.52174	50	50.00	50
$m=3$	6.67529	6.74813	6.79683	36	42.24	50
$m=3.5$	6.73916	6.75495	6.78513	27	30.80	36

Fig. 2. Clustering results of FCM with grid points.

randomly generated Normal-4 data sets. The results are shown in Table II. Yu et al. [14] concluded that the theoretical valid m for a random Normal-4 data set should be not greater than 2.6 which sample mean is an optimizer with approximately 50% probability. In Table II, when $m=2.5$, the worst case is the sample mean being the unique optimizer with $MSE=6.52$. When $m=3$ and 3.5 , the FCM always produce the unique optimizer \bar{x} . These results are coincident to Yu et al. [14]. Although a too large m may cough trouble in FCM, a suitable large m value can make FCM more robust to noise and outlier. We will discuss this property in next subsection.

IV. ROBUST ANALYSIS OF FUZZY C-MEANS

The influence curve (IC) can help us to assess the relative influence of an individual observation toward the value of an estimate. The influence function of an M-estimator is proportional to its φ function [17]. If the influence function of an estimator is unbounded, an outlier might cause trouble where the φ function is used to denote the degree of the influence. Let the loss between the data point x_j and cluster center a_i be

$$\rho(x_j - a_i) = \mu_{ij}^m \|x_j - a_i\|^2 \quad (4)$$

and

$$\varphi(x_j - a_i) = \frac{d}{da_i} \rho(x_j - a_i) = -2\mu_{ij}^m (x_j - a_i) \quad (5)$$

By solving the equation $\sum_{j=1}^n \varphi(x_j - a_i) = 0$, we have the result shown in Equation (3). Thus, the FCM cluster center estimate is an M-estimator with the loss function (4) and φ function (5). Refer to Figs. 1(a)~1(d), the corresponding φ functions with different m are illustrated in Figs. 1(e)~1(h). The influences of adding a point on the cluster center 0 will become very small when m is large. That is, FCM can be robust to noise and outliers with a large m value. Figure 2 is a simple example to illustrate this phenomenon.

This is an artificial data set with grid points. We implement FCM with different m values and the results are shown in Figs. 2(a), 2(d) and 2(g). We then add an outlier point in the coordinate (50,50) and the results are shown in Figs. 2(b), 2(e) and 2(h). Moreover, we add one more outlier point in the coordinate (100,100) and the results are shown in Figs. 2(c), 2(f) and 2(i). These results are coincident to the phenomenon illustrated in Fig. 1. We also implement the IRIS data set [15,16] to test the influences of parameter m on the results of FCM. The IRIS data set has $n = 150$ points in an $s = 4$ dimensional space. It consists of three clusters with Iris Setosa, Iris Versicolor and

Fig. 3. The error counts of IRIS data set.

Iris Virginica. Two clusters have substantial overlapping. The clustering error counts of this data are approximate 16. Figure 3 shows the clustering error counts of the IRIS data obtained by FCM with different m values ($m=1.1, 1.5, 2, 3, 4, \dots, 50$). The error counts are approximate 13 when m is large. These examples reveal the robust properties of FCM when m becomes large.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Note that, when m tends to infinity, the φ function of a finite point x_j will tend to 0. However, in real application, we never observe an infinity data point. We then have

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \varphi(x_j - a_i) = 0 \quad (6)$$

for a real data point. That is, a very large m value will make FCM very robust. However, this is not a good guideline for selecting m in FCM. Although FCM becomes very robust in a large m case, the membership value for each data point will very close to $1/c$ in this case and the sample mean will become the unique optimizer. Figure 1(d) also shows that the membership values for the data points becomes closed to 0.5 when $m=6$. Here, we suggest implementing FCM with $m \in [1.5, 4]$ under the restriction that m is smaller than the theoretical upper bound proposed by Yu et al. [14].

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